

THE BENEFITS OF HAVING OVERALL 7.0 FROM IELTS IN DIFFERENT AREAS OF LIFE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6555025>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th May 2022

Accepted: 10th May 2022

Online: 15th May 2022

KEY WORDS

IELTS candidates, valid test, reliable score, language skills, merits, English qualifications, good language user, immigration conveniences.

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, the commonality of English language makes it demand for almost everyone to learn this language and prove their knowledge with having the official test certificate. In this matter, IELTS is the most reliable one which is accepted internationally. Also, scoring overall 7.0 from IELTS can have a lot of benefits to the test takers. This paper is going to look at the most widely known advantages of having this score.

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, it is more than important to know English language almost in everywhere. However, while considering to have academic language tests, many people get confused as they do not own proper knowledge of this issue. Surprisingly, many opt for IELTS test. Because it is believed to be valid at the same time popular test type. And managing to score 7.0 is not an easy job for a second language learner. So, many people are probably interested in knowing what are the advantages of having this score. Therefore, in my research, I am going to provide the reader with possible merits to the society and to IELTS candidates themselves.

1.0 The Importance of Having IELTS Certificate Nowadays

We all know that today the reputation of English language is becoming higher and higher and most countries are still accepting this language as an official second language in their countries. So, naturally, all the networks are highly demanding English in the workplaces. Not only this, but also a large amount of data in the Internet could easily be found in this language, while this is so hard to find some data in other languages. Thus, to show our language skills in practice we need to learn English profoundly and then, for our understanding of English, there needs to be a legal document. This document is the IELTS (International English language testing system) certificate. One difference

of this certificate from other language testing systems is that it is widely available test type throughout the globe and almost everyone is aware of this certificate. One more thing that makes it more popular is its validity. I mean the IELTS test is quite fair and shows true language knowledge of the candidates. Also, it tests the most necessary skills such as listening, reading, writing and speaking that one should acquire in order to communicate in this language.

According to the official test taking agency called British Council, "Taking the IELTS test opens doors – it can help you study, live or work almost anywhere around the world. More than 9,000 organisations worldwide recognise the IELTS (International English Language Testing System) certification, including government, academic and employment institutions." (British Council, 2022); That clearly shows that perhaps the most reliable language test for English is IELTS as it could be accepted by almost any organization including job places, education organizations and other key places in any time in the world. I think it is noticeable from all the given why it is so important for every language learner to take the IELTS EXAM first before thinking other types of language tests.

2.0 The common benefits of having IELTS overall 7, C1 level

C1 level in English means advanced level and advanced level user of English language at the same time according to Cambridge English Assessment means "C1 Advanced, formerly known as Cambridge English: Advanced (CAE), is one of our Cambridge English Qualifications. It is the in-depth, high-level qualification that

shows you have the language skills that employers and universities are looking for." (CAE, 2022); Therefore, I believe that it is important to note that C1 user of English is someone who can actually use English very good.

Next, when it comes to its benefits, first one definitely would be knowing yourself as a person who can speak English well, which boosts self-confidence. Also, personally, individuals with C1 level have a good reputation and usually well-respected anywhere. Additionally, there are international benefits as well which outweigh personal benefits. During my research and asking from former IELTS candidates who were able to score overall 7 in their tests, I noticed some of the most common benefits of owning 7.

➤ Immigration conveniences

Most candidates mentioned that it becomes relatively easy to travel to another country with IELTS as one is able to understand others in another place. Also, in the airport departments taking VISA cards is easier with IELTS.

➤ Job Prospects

Almost every employee nowadays is in demand of people who knows more than one language. So, it becomes really easy for one to pass the interview with the certificate. Furthermore, candidates with high band score from IELTS always stand out among other people on the interview. While this fact is so true, there is another thing also which makes this statement more true. Even in the workplace, there are more chances of promotions, free travel opportunities for office workers with IELTS than others.

➤ Study

Probably, the opportunities that IELTS gives students in education is the

best and the pleasant one of everyone. Briefly, to achieve special scholarships and get accepted to the international universities, at least IELTS 7.0 is on demand. So, the first thing all these people who want to accomplish their goals, firstly need to take into consideration the idea of achieving IELTS 7.0.

➤ **Critical thinking**

So, while students are on their journey towards success, they notice that they are not only acquiring language skills, but also working on their education, life experience. This journey gives IELTS candidates high critical thinking ability. For one to achieve 7, it is a necessity to develop critical thinking, which helps them a lot more than they think in the future.

➤ **Better Communication skills**

Unsurprisingly, for the speaking test one needs to develop speaking skills which involves communication skills as well. According to Kings College, "When you

learn English as a second language, you are also learning new ways to think and express yourself both verbally and through the written word. Learning multiple languages can help you communicate more clearly in any language as you learn more about how language itself works and how to use it to communicate with others in all kinds of social, educational and professional settings." (Kings College, 2020)

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in a global level, having IELTS certificate matter a lot for almost everyone and scoring overall 7.0 is an amazing job which brings a myriad number of benefits in one's life. So, by doing this research work, I've analyzed these benefits and made necessary conclusions. My observations hopefully bear good fruits and through this paper, individuals find ease in understanding their 7.0 score if they get this band.

References:

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